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1 **Identification of novel metabolomic biomarkers in an experimental model**
2 **of septic acute kidney injury**

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ABSTRACT

27 The aim of this study is the identification of metabolomic biomarkers of sepsis and sepsis-
28 induced acute kidney injury (AKI) in an experimental model. Pigs were anesthetized and
29 monitored to measure mean arterial pressure (MAP), systemic blood flow (Q_T), mean
30 pulmonary arterial pressure (MPAP), renal artery blood flow (Q_{RA}), renal cortical blood flow
31 (Q_{RC}), and urine output (UO). Sepsis was induced at t=0 min by the administration of live
32 *Escherichia coli* (n=6) or saline (n=8). At t=300 min, animals were sacrificed. Renal tissue,
33 urine and serum samples were analyzed by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)
34 spectroscopy. Principal component analyses were performed on the processed NMR spectra
35 to highlight kidney injury biomarkers. Sepsis was associated with decreased Q_T and MAP,
36 and decreased Q_{RA} , Q_{RC} and urine output. Creatinine serum concentration and neutrophil
37 gelatinase-associated lipocalin serum and urine concentrations increased. NMR-based
38 metabolomics analysis found metabolic differences between control and septic animals: (i)
39 in kidney tissue, increased lactate and nicotinuric acid, and decreased valine, aspartate,
40 glucose and threonine; (ii) in urine, increased isovaleroglycine, aminoadipic acid, N-
41 acetylglutamine, N-acetylaspartate and ascorbic acid, and decreased myoinositol and
42 phenylacetyl glycine; (iii) in serum, increased lactate, alanine, pyruvate and glutamine, and
43 decreased valine, glucose and betaine concentrations. The concentration of several
44 metabolites altered in renal tissue and urine samples from septic animals showed a
45 significant correlation with markers of AKI (i.e., creatinine and NGAL serum
46 concentrations). NMR-based metabolomics is a potentially useful tool for biomarker
47 identification of sepsis-induced AKI.

48 **Key words:** Acute kidney injury, metabolomics, biomarker, sepsis, Nuclear Magnetic
49 Resonance

50 INTRODUCTION

51 Sepsis and septic shock are important risk factors for acute kidney injury (AKI). It is
52 estimated that 64% of patients with sepsis suffer AKI, and AKI is associated with an excess
53 mortality in critically ill patients(2). Despite its prevalence and associated mortality, our
54 understanding of the pathogenesis of septic AKI is limited. Renal vasoconstriction and
55 reduced renal blood flow leading to renal ischemia, as well as inflammation and apoptosis of
56 renal tubular cells are contributing factors to kidney injury in sepsis.

57 Currently the diagnosis of sepsis-induced AKI is based on changes in urine output and
58 creatinine serum concentration. Recently proposed biomarkers include serum and urine
59 neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL), cystatin C, urine IL-18 and KIM-1(21,
60 28). However, these biomarkers lack sufficient specificity and sensitivity. For instance,
61 NGAL is released from activated neutrophils, and serum concentration increases in sepsis
62 regardless of renal function. Thus the search of biomarkers of sepsis-induced organ
63 dysfunction in general and AKI in particular is of clinical relevance for early diagnosis and
64 for the identification of potential therapeutic targets. In addition, the biological function of
65 the identified molecules could shed light into as yet unidentified pathogenetic mechanisms.

66 Metabolomics is the global study of the products of cellular metabolic reactions. ¹H-nuclear
67 magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy of biological samples provides a tool for
68 understanding the changes of metabolic patterns in response to various stimuli. ¹H-NMR
69 spectroscopy has been used for the diagnosis of sepsis in experimental models (14) and
70 clinical samples (31), and to predict outcome in patients with sepsis (10). Several studies
71 have utilized metabolomics to study AKI induced by toxins and antibiotics (35), and
72 recently a metabolomics approach has been used in a pilot study to discover novel serum
73 biomarkers of AKI (32).

74 The present study was designed to identify metabolomic biomarkers in an experimental
75 model of sepsis. Unlike preceding studies, we analyzed different biological samples, such as
76 kidney tissue, urine and serum in order to correlate urine and/or serum biomarkers with the
77 kidney metabolome. These biomarkers were used for the identification of metabolic
78 pathways affected in AKI. In addition, the physiological relevance of the identified

79 metabolomic abnormalities was further substantiated by showing their correlation with
80 parameters indicative of renal injury and dysfunction.

81 **MATERIAL AND METHODS**

82 **Animal preparation**

83 All animals were treated in accordance with the guidelines approved by the Spanish
84 Scientific Procedures Act (32/2007) and the European Union Directive 86/609/EEC.

85 After overnight fasting, male pigs weighing 27 ± 4 kg (mean \pm SD), were sedated
86 intramuscularly with ketamine hydrochloride ($10 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$) and midazolam ($0.5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$).
87 After cannulation of an ear vein, propofol ($2 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ intravenous [iv] bolus followed by a
88 continuous iv infusion at $10 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$), fentanyl ($5 \text{ mcg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) and atracurium ($0.5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)
89 were administered. The left external jugular vein was then cannulated and used later for
90 the administration of sedative solutions, iv fluids and the *E. coli* infusion.

91 A tracheostomy was performed and an endotracheal tube was introduced and connected to a
92 volumetric ventilator (Servo 900C, Siemens Elena, Sweden) with the following settings:
93 respiratory rate = 20 bpm, $V_T = 15 \text{ ml} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$, $\text{FiO}_2 = 0.50$, PEEP = +5 cm H_2O .

94 The right carotid artery was cannulated for mean arterial pressure (MAP) monitoring.

95 A pulmonary artery catheter was inserted through the right jugular vein for measuring right
96 arterial pressure (RAP), mean pulmonary artery pressure (MPAP), pulmonary artery
97 occlusion pressure (PAOP), and systemic blood flow (Q_T , by the thermodilution technique).

98 A small supra-pubic incision was made to perform a cystostomy, and a urinary catheter was
99 introduced into the urinary bladder for measurement of urine output.

100 A right-sided lumbotomy was made and a retroperitoneal dissection was performed to expose
101 the right renal artery and vein. A transit time flow probe was placed around the renal artery,
102 and a laser doppler flowmeter was positioned on the kidney surface, for measuring,
103 respectively, renal artery (Q_{RA}) and renal cortical (Q_{RC}) blood flows. Normal saline (0.9%)
104 was administered throughout the experiment ($4 \text{ ml} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) in both groups.

105

106

107 **Protocol**

108 After instrumentation, a 30 min resting period was allowed, and arterial blood gases were
109 obtained to prove normal blood gases. Two groups of pigs were studied: non-septic (n=8),
110 and septic (n=6). At t=0 min live *E. coli* (1.5×10^8 /kg CFU, serotype 5044552, isolated from
111 blood cultures from a patient with septic shock) or an equivalent amount of saline, were
112 infused over 30 min.

113 At different points in time, from t=-10 min to t=300 min, we measured MAP, RAP, MPAP,
114 PAOP, Q_T , and Q_{RA} and Q_{RC} . Blood samples were obtained at baseline and at t=300 min for
115 the biochemical measurements.

116 After the observation period, animals were sacrificed by a thiopental overdose. The left
117 kidney was identified through the previous lumbotomy, and a tissue sample from the inferior
118 renal pole was fixed in formaldehyde 4% for histological analysis. The upper renal pole was
119 frozen at -80° C for $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy analysis.

120 **Hemodynamic measurements and calculations**

121 Pressures were measured and displayed (Hewlett Packard, Model 66S, Geneva, Switzerland).
122 Systemic blood flow was measured by the thermodilution technique (CO computer, Abbott
123 Labs, Chicago IL, 60064). Q_{RA} was measured by a doppler flowmeter (*4 mm, Transonics*
124 *Systems, Ithaca, NY, USA*) and Q_{RC} was measured by a laser doppler flowmeter (*Transonic*
125 *System model T106 small animal blood flow meter*). Vascular resistances were calculated
126 using conventional formulae.

127 **Biochemical measurements**

128 Arterial blood samples were obtained for measurement of complete blood cell count (Coulter
129 analyzer); urea and creatinine serum concentrations (Hitachi 911, Boehringer Mannheim,
130 Germany); arterial blood gases (ABL 500, Radiometer, Copenhagen); and NGAL serum
131 concentration (ELISA Kit BioPorto, Denmark). NGAL concentration was also measured in
132 urine samples.

133

134

135 **Light microscopy**

136 The formalin-fixed tissue was embedded in paraffin, cut in 4 μm -thick sections and stained
137 with hematoxylin-eosine and periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) for the enhancement of the basement
138 membrane material. Glomerular, tubule-interstitial and vascular changes were analyzed.

139 **NMR data acquisition**

140 Intact kidney tissue (weighing approx. 10 mg) and serum samples (40 μl of serum) were
141 examined using High Resolution – Magic Angle Spinning (HR-MAS) ^1H -NMR spectroscopy
142 operating at 4 $^\circ\text{C}$ to reduce metabolic degradation. ^1H -NMR spectroscopy was performed at
143 500.13 MHz using a Bruker AMX500 spectrometer 11.7 T. Samples were placed into a 50 μl
144 zirconium oxide rotor using a rinsed with a cylindrical insert, together with 15 μl of 0.1mM
145 solution of TSP in deuterium water (D_2O), and spun at 4000 Hz spinning rate to remove the
146 effects of spinning side bands from the acquired spectra. Urine samples were centrifuged
147 (8000 rpm for 5 min at 4 $^\circ\text{C}$) to remove cells and other precipitated material. Then, 400 μL of
148 supernatant were mixed with 60 μL of buffer solution (KH_2PO_4 1.5 M in D_2O) containing
149 0.1% trimethylsilyl propionate (TSP), used as chemical shift reference. Fine pH adjustment to
150 7.00 \pm 0.02 was carried out by adding a few drops of 4 M solutions of KOD or DCl. Samples
151 were transferred to a 5 mm NMR tube and examined using a Bruker AV500 spectrometer
152 operating at 4 $^\circ\text{C}$. Magnetic field homogeneity was optimized based on glucose signal at
153 4.65ppm (doublet) and lactate signal at 4.10 ppm (quadruplet). The datasets generated for this
154 study can be found in the figshare repository <https://figshare.com/s/2d1c1cf7aeb206191df7> .

155 A number of bidimensional homonuclear and heteronuclear experiments such as standard
156 gradient-enhanced Correlation Spectroscopy (COSY), ^1H - ^1H Total Correlated Spectroscopy
157 (TOCSY) and Gradient-selected Hetero-nuclear Single Quantum Correlation (HSQC)
158 protocols, were performed to carry out the components assignments. Between consecutive
159 2D spectra, a control ^1H NMR spectrum was always measured. No gross degradation was
160 noted in the signals of multiple spectra acquired under the same conditions.

161 Standard solvent suppressed spectra were grouped into 16,000 data points, averaged over
162 256 acquisitions. The data acquisition lasted in total 13 min using a sequence based on the
163 first increment of the Nuclear Overhauser Effect Spectroscopy (NOESY) pulse sequence to
164 effect suppression of the water resonance and limit the effect of B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneities

165 in the spectra (relaxation delay-90°-t1-90°-tm-90°-acquire Free Induction Decay (FID)
166 signal) in which a secondary radio frequency irradiation field was applied at the water
167 resonance frequency during the relaxation delay of 2 s and during the mixing period (tm =
168 150 ms), with t1 fixed at 3 s. Samples acquisitions were performed using a spectral width
169 of 8333.33 Hz. Prior to Fourier transformation, the FID signals were multiplied by an
170 exponential weight function corresponding to a line broadening of 0.3 Hz. Spectra were
171 referenced to the TSP singlet at 0 ppm chemical shift.

172 A standard gradient-enhanced Correlation Spectroscopy (COSY) protocol was acquired
173 under the following conditions: water presaturation during relaxation delay, spectral width of
174 5122.95 Hz in both dimensions, 2000 data points in f2 and 256 increments in f1. An
175 unshifted sinusoidal window function was applied in both dimensions and zero filling in f1
176 dimension. ¹H-¹H Total Correlated Spectroscopy (TOCSY) experiment was registered in
177 the Time-Proportional Phase Incrementation (TPPI) phase sensitive mode, water pre-
178 saturation during 1s relaxation delay, a spectral width of 5122.95 Hz in both dimensions,
179 60ms mixing time, 2000 data points in f2 and 256 increments in f1. Zero filling in f1 and
180 unshifted squared sinusoidal window function in both dimensions were applied before
181 Fourier transformation.

182 Gradient-selected Heteronuclear Single Quantum Correlation (HSQC) experiments of
183 serum and tissue samples were registered with the following parameters: 95 μs for Globally
184 Optimized Alternating Phase Rectangular Pulse (GARP) ¹³C decoupling, 8333Hz and 21
185 kHz spectral widths in the ¹H and ¹³C dimensions, respectively, 2000 data points in f₂ and
186 256 increments in f₁. Zero filling in f₁ and unshifted squared sinusoidal window function in
187 both dimensions were applied before Fourier transformation.

188 **Spectral processing**

189 Spectra processing was automatically performed using the “Metabonomic” R package (15).
190 The chemical shift region from 5.00–5.20 ppm was excluded from the analysis in order to
191 remove the random effects of variation in the water resonance suppression. Similarly, the
192 chemical shift region from 0 to 0.04 ppm containing the internal reference (TSP) was
193 excluded from the statistical analyses. ¹H NMR spectra were automatically data-reduced to
194 integral segments or buckets of equal length (δ0.01 ppm for renal tissue and serum spectra

195 and δ 0.04 ppm for urine spectra) in order to compensate variations in resonance positions
196 (11) and they were normalized to total sum of the spectral regions. Relative intensity was
197 calculated as the original intensity normalized to total sum of the spectral regions. 2D
198 spectral processing and editing was performed with MestRenova v. 7.1.1 (Mestrelab
199 Research S.L., Santiago de Compostela, Spain).

200 **Statistical analysis**

201 Hemodynamic and biochemical variables were compared by the Student's t test. The
202 correlation between each metabolite and several physiological parameters at t=5 h was
203 assessed by Spearman's rank correlation analysis. A p value <0.05 was considered
204 statistically significant. Data are shown as mean \pm SD. We used the statistical package SPSS
205 17.0 (Chicago, IL).

206 Principal Components Analysis (PCA) (12) was applied in order to extract the most
207 discriminative spectral subset from the total pool of metabolites. Number of principal
208 components was selected based on model robustness parameters: $R^2 > 0.8$, Variance
209 Explained $> 50\%$ and Mean Squared Error of Prediction (MSEP) minimization in leave-
210 one-out cross-validation (4). The potential biomarkers selected from PCA loading matrix
211 were confirmed from partial least squares (PLS) correlation plots by Hotelling's T2 test.
212 The metabolomics statistical computing were also performed with the "Metabonomic" R
213 package (15). The resonances identified as significantly different by Hotelling's T2 test
214 were individually integrated for metabolic quantification using the Global Spectral
215 Deconvolution algorithm of MestRenova v. 8.1 (Mestrelab Research S.L., Santiago de
216 Compostela, Spain). For the metabolic quantification, statistical significance was
217 determined using a Bonferroni corrected Student's t test (33) assuming unequal variance
218 with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

219 **RESULTS**

220 **Hemodynamic changes**

221 Administration of *E. coli* induced systemic hypotension, pulmonary hypertension, and a
222 decrease in Q_{RA} and Q_{RC} , as compared to control animals. Q_T tended to decrease. No
223 significant differences were found in RAP measurements (**Table 1**).

224 **Biochemical changes**

225 Creatinine and urea serum concentration increased over time and urine output decreased in
226 septic as compared to control pigs (Table 1). NGAL serum and urine concentration were
227 higher in septic as compared to control animals at the end of the experiment (**Figure 1**).

228 **Histological changes**

229 Kidney tissue samples from animals with sepsis showed marked abnormalities, including
230 tubular degeneration, tubular dilation, luminal congestion and disseminated intravascular
231 coagulation (**Figure 2**). Tissue samples from control animals were normal at light
232 microscopy.

233 **Metabolomic Analysis**

234 Unsupervised classification studies with PCA were carried out to analyze differences
235 between spectra from septic and control pigs. Three principal components were selected to
236 build the PCA based on model robustness parameters, e.g. R^2 , Variance Explained and
237 MSE in leave-one-out cross-validation (**Figure 3**). PCAs (**Figure 4**) provided a nearly
238 perfect discrimination between the two groups along the first principal components (PC1).
239 Metabolites present in kidney tissue, urine and serum samples were identified according to
240 the Human Metabolome Database (36), and characteristic cross-peaks from 2D spectra to
241 help in the unequivocal assignment of these metabolites. Metabolic differences elicited by
242 our method between both groups are highlighted in representative kidney tissue, urine and
243 serum spectra (**Figure 5**). As compared with the control group, animals with sepsis showed
244 in kidney tissue higher concentrations of lactate and nicotinuric acid, whereas valine,
245 aspartate, glucose and threonine concentrations decreased; in urine, isovaleroglycine,
246 aminodipic acid, N-acetylglutamine, N-acetylaspartate, and ascorbic acid concentrations
247 increased, whereas myoinositol and phenylacetyl glycine concentrations decreased; in

248 serum, lactate, alanine, pyruvate and glutamine concentrations increased; and valine,
249 glucose and betaine concentrations decreased. (**Table 2**).

250 **Correlation between metabolome and markers of kidney injury or dysfunction**

251 Several metabolites which concentration changed in sepsis as compared to control animals,
252 both in kidney tissue and urine, showed a significant correlation with creatinine and NGAL
253 serum concentration at t=5 h (**Table 3**).

254 **DISCUSSION**

255 The early diagnosis of sepsis is crucial for timely and effective treatment, and biomarkers
256 of sepsis-induced organ dysfunction, such as AKI, are needed. Although most studies on
257 biomarkers for early diagnosis of AKI have focused on specific proteins, some studies have
258 utilized metabolomics to study AKI induced by toxins and antibiotics (3, 24, 30, 37). The
259 early metabolomic approach to identify possible biomarkers of kidney injury is of interest,
260 as the usual clinical measures lack sufficient specificity and sensitivity. In the present
261 study, we used NMR-based metabolomic analysis to describe the metabolome
262 characteristic of sepsis-induced AKI. As our model features biochemical and
263 morphological changes consistent with sepsis-induced AKI, we correlated the degree of
264 kidney injury and dysfunction with the magnitude of change of different metabolites
265 identified by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy. As far as we know, this is the first study describing
266 the change in the concentration of several metabolites in renal tissue, urine and serum using
267 ¹H-NMR spectroscopy in a large animal model of sepsis induced AKI. We confirmed the
268 metabolomic changes associated with sepsis previously reported in serum and urine
269 samples by our group (14) and others (20, 31) in animal models and in patients (23). We
270 also found a correlation of some biomarkers measured in kidney tissue and in urine with
271 parameters indicative of kidney injury. The metabolites identified suggest involvement of
272 several metabolic pathways in sepsis-induced AKI.

273 Our findings of decreased levels of **glucose** and increased **lactate, pyruvate and alanine** in
274 serum, indicate alterations of cellular energy pathways. These metabolic changes have been
275 previously reported as markers of cell death and tissue damage in sepsis animal models (14,
276 20, 31). The significant correlation between serum lactate levels and NGAL serum
277 concentration supports a relationship between elevated serum lactate and kidney injury,
278 likely due to tissue dysoxia, as also suggested by the higher lactate and decreased glucose
279 concentrations in renal tissue.

280 In the same line, we also detected biomarkers of fat breakdown. The observed changes in
281 **nicotinuric acid concentration in kidney tissue and phenilacetylglycine and**
282 **isovaleroglycine concentration in urine** may indicate an alteration in fatty acid
283 metabolism. Acyl glycines are normally minor metabolites of fatty acids. However, the

284 excretion of certain acyl glycines is associated with mitochondrial fatty acid beta-oxidation
285 dysfunction(19). Phenylacetylglycine has been previously identified, among other fatty acid
286 catabolites, as early biomarker of kidney dysfunction in a murine model of
287 ischemia/reperfusion injury (34). In line with this finding, we found a significant
288 correlation between phenylacetylglycine urine concentration and NGAL serum
289 concentration.

290 We found that **valine, aspartate and threonine** concentrations decreased in kidney tissue.
291 These results are consistent with earlier reports describing the increase in amino acid
292 excretion as a potential marker for kidney dysfunction (25, 37). In certain conditions such
293 as sepsis or kidney dysfunction, the defense and repair processes dramatically increase the
294 demand of amino acids, especially **threonine**, for proteins synthesis (6, 7). In another
295 metabolomics study of nephrotoxicity, Boudonck et al.(3) reported a decrease in amino
296 acids and nucleosides in kidney tissue, including **valine, aspartate and threonine**.
297 Aspartate is a precursor to many other cofactors or compounds involved in cellular
298 signaling including **N-acetylaspartate** and **alanine**. N-acetylaspartate is substrate for the
299 enzyme aspartoacylase-2 that plays an important role in deacetylating mercapturic acids in
300 kidney proximal tubules. Our finding of increased urine concentration of N-acetylaspartate
301 is in line with previous publications, where NMR-based metabolomic analysis of
302 mercapturic acids was proposed as biomarker of renal injury (22). Similarly, urinary
303 **aminoadipic acid** has been proposed as a biomarker of protein oxidation during sepsis
304 (29). Other studies have also proposed N-acetylglutamine as a marker of renal dysfunction
305 in patients treated with aminoglycosides and glycopeptides (26).

306 Sepsis and severe infection cause marked derangements in the flow of glutamine among
307 organs (16). **Glutamine** is required for the tissue response to catabolic processes,
308 inflammation and infection (38). Skeletal muscle and the lungs exhibit a significant
309 increase in glutamine release to the circulation during infection, whereas the liver becomes
310 the major glutamine consumer (1). The role of endogenous glutamine in kidney function is
311 not completely understood. Some studies have proposed that the administration of
312 exogenous glutamine have a protective effect in the kidney (13, 17). Similarly, it has been
313 observed that **ascorbic acid** attenuates lung and kidney injury induced by abdominal sepsis

314 (8, 9) or contrast induced-acute kidney injury (27), thus the observed increased of urinary
315 ascorbic acid observed in sepsis may indicate a protective mechanism.

316 We also found decreased concentration of betaine in serum and myoinositol in kidney
317 tissue. **Betaine** plays a role in the manufacture of carnitine and serves to protect the kidneys
318 from bacterial growth (5). Interestingly, both betaine and **myo-inositol** play crucial roles in
319 cell osmoregulation in the thick ascending limb of Henle (18). Thus the observed decreased
320 concentration of these metabolites could be related to sepsis-induced decreased cell defense
321 mechanisms and tubular dysfunction.

322 Finally, we detected nonsignificant changes in ethanol concentration in urine samples, most
323 probably from bacterial metabolism. Ethanol production may suggest a switch of the
324 glycolysis to a fermentative metabolism in microorganisms that causes bacteremia, and it
325 has been reported as a negative prognostic biomarker in sepsis patients (10). No other
326 signals of metabolites of exclusive bacterial origin were detected.

327 The novel findings herein reported have to be interpreted considering at least some
328 limitations: (i) the spectroscopic findings in kidney tissue samples lack clinical relevance,
329 as these samples cannot be obtained in clinical practice; (ii) we cannot conclude as to the
330 usefulness of the reported findings for early diagnosis of sepsis; and (iii) we cannot
331 determine whether the reported changes in urine and serum samples are specific for AKI
332 induced by sepsis, or are rather related to other sepsis-induced organ dysfunction.

333 In summary, we here report specific metabolites identified by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy that
334 characteristically change in a sepsis large animal model. To our knowledge, this is the first
335 study in a large animal model describing the metabolic reprogramming induced by sepsis in
336 kidney tissue. The physiological relevance of the findings herein reported is substantiated
337 by the significant correlation between the concentration of some of the altered metabolites
338 and parameters indicative of kidney dysfunction (creatinine serum concentration) or injury
339 (NGAL serum concentration). However, whether the reported metabolomic changes have
340 pathophysiological implications remains to be proven.

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478 **Figure and tables legends**

479 **Figure 1.** (A) Total urine output. (B) Urine and serum NGAL

480 **Figure 2.** Photomicrograph (light microscopy, hematoxylin and eosin X40) of
481 representative kidney slices. A: Normal glomerulus from a control animal. B: Kidney tissue
482 from a septic animal (PAS stain, 40x). Changes consistent with thrombotic
483 microangiopathy, with numerous PAS-positive microthrombi occluding the lumina of
484 glomerular capillaries in a diffuse pattern are seen.

485 **Figure 3.** PCA robustness parameters from kidney tissue (A), urine (B) and plasma (C):
486 Variance Explained (left), R2 (center) and Mean Squared Error of Prediction in leave-one-
487 out cross-validation (right)

488 **Figure 4.** Score plots of PCAs performed on the ¹H-NMR spectra. A, kidney tissue. B,
489 urine. C, serum. Control (red circles) and septic pigs (blue triangles) are clearly separated in
490 the three score plots.

491 **Figure 5.** Representative ¹H NMR spectra of kidney tissue (A), urine (B) and serum (C)
492 samples from septic pigs.

493 **Table 1.** Changes in hemodynamic and biochemical parameters induced by sepsis.

494 **Table 2.** Summary of significant spectral regions of postulated metabolites and their
495 relative amounts from control and septic animals.

496 **Table 3.** Correlation between biomarkers of AKI (serum concentration of creatinine and
497 NGAL) and different metabolites by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy.

A

* p < 0.05 vs Control. Urine output in ml

B

NGALs (micg/ug), NGALu (micg/ml), * p < 0.05 vs Control

A

Table 1. Changes in hemodynamic and biochemical parameters induced by sepsis.

		t=0 min	t=300 min	p value
MAP (mmHg)	Control	106.8 ± 39.8	89.3 ± 18.4	0.10
	Sepsis	95.2 ± 14.9	51.2 ± 21.3	0.04
MPAP (mmHg)	Control	25.2 ± 5.8	23.1 ± 6.6	0.20
	Sepsis	24.5 ± 9.8	43.3 ± 9.8	0.01
RAP (mmHg)	Control	11.1 ± 3.1	10.2 ± 2.6	0.30
	Sepsis	12.5 ± 5.2	10.6 ± 1.5	0.60
Q_T (l/min)	Control	3.1 ± 1.4	2.4 ± 1.1	0.40
	Sepsis	2.6 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.3	0.03
Q_{RA} (mL/seg)	Control	142.4 ± 72.7	148.3 ± 71.9	0.40
	Sepsis	139.5 ± 71.5	29.6 ± 43.9	0.01
Q_{RC} (AU)	Control	58.6 ± 21.9	62,9 ± 19.3	0.40
	Sepsis	66.8 ± 15.9	28.4 ± 15.8	0.04
Urea (mmol/L)	Control	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.40
	Sepsis	0.2 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.01
Creatinine (mg/dl)	Control	1.0 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	0.10
	Sepsis	1.0 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.2	0.01

p values refer to the comparison t=0 vs t=300 in both groups for each parameter.

MAP, mean arterial pressure; MPAP, mean pulmonary artery pressure; Q_T, systemic blood flow; Q_{RA}, renal artery blood flow; Q_{RC}, cortical renal blood flow; AU, arbitrary units.

Table 2. Summary of significant spectral regions of postulated metabolites and their relative amounts from control and septic animals.

Sample	NMR position (ppm)	Postulated metabolites	Relative intensity		P value
			Control	Sepsis	
Renal tissue	1.07	Valine	2.16 ± 0.10	1.33 ± 0.08	7.06E-03
	2.71	Aspartate	2.06 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.02	5.45E-03
	3.47	Glucose	1.02 ± 0.04	0.43 ± 0.02	1.56E-03
	3.58	Threonine	7.17 ± 0.12	4.27 ± 0.12	4.26E-03
	4.11	Lactate	0.40 ± 0.07	1.00 ± 0.09	1.93E-02
	8.25	Nicotinuric Acid	0.10 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.01	3.87E-04
Urine	0.93	Isovaleroglycine	1.55 ± 0.05	6.16 ± 0.09	1.57E-02
	1.85	Amino adipic acid	0.53 ± 0.05	1.16 ± 0.06	4.40E-03
	2.48	N-acetylglutamine	0.18 ± 0.02	4.68 ± 0.75	2.16E-02
	2.78	N-acetylaspartate	0.19 ± 0.02	1.35 ± 0.49	2.04E-02
	3.59	Myoinositol	24.26 ± 1.01	13.42 ± 0.81	4.36E-03
	4.51	Ascorbic Acid	0.66 ± 0.02	1.86 ± 0.08	1.13E-02
	7.32	Phenylacetyl glycine	38.80 ± 2.15	18.64 ± 1.6	2.87E-03
Serum	1.07	Valine	3.28 ± 0.44	2.26 ± 0.88	3.30E-02
	1.48	Alanine	5.89 ± 2.86	15.20 ± 4.09	1.61E-03
	2.38	Pyruvate	1.44 ± 0.18	3.56 ± 0.26	6.54E-08
	2.46	Glutamine	0.95 ± 0.58	1.81 ± 0.32	1.70E-02
	3.25	Betaine	8.22 ± 1.15	3.88 ± 1.57	5.14E-04
	3.47	Glucose	14.74 ± 3.02	4.86 ± 2.99	4.20E-04
	4.11	Lactate	3.11 ± 0.15	12.36 ± 5.42	2.23E-03

Data are expressed as mean ± SD. Signal intensities were normalized for the total sum of the spectral regions to calculate their relative intensity.

Table 3. Correlation between biomarkers of AKI (serum concentration of creatinine and NGAL) and different metabolites by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy.

Metabolite	Creatinine		NGALsNGAL	
	R ²	p value	R ²	p value
Renal tissue				
Valine	0.61	0.001	0.82	0.001
Aspartate	0.60	0.01	0.71	0.01
Urine				
Phenylacetylglycine	0.66	0.02	0.71	0.01
Serum				
Glucose	0.69	0.001	0.82	0.001
Betaine	0.71	0.001	0.83	0.001